

JANUBIY-SHARQIY FARG'ONA AGROTSENOZLARI TUNLAMSIMON KAPALAKLARNING XO'JALIK AHAMIYATI

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Abdikaxarov Bekzod Dilmurod o'g'li

Farg'ona davlat universiteti o'qituvchisi

bekzod.abdikakhorov.94@gmail.com

Anotatsiya

Tunlamsimon kapalaklarning qurtlari tadqiqot hududi janubiy-sharqiy Farg'ona agrotsenozlarida keng tarqalgan zarar keltirish darajasiga ko'ra 3 ta pog'onaga ajratiladi zarar keltiradigan turlar soni 19 ta kam zarar keltiradigan turlar soni 14 tani tashkil qiladi. Tunlamsimon kapalaklarning 8 ta turlari *Mythimna unipuncta*, *Heliothis peltigera*, *Helicoverpa armigera*, *Spodoptera exigua*, *Mamestra =Barathra brassicae*, *Agrotis exclamationis*, *Agrotis ipsilon*, *Agrotis segetum*) tadqiqot hududi agrotsenozlarida dominant fitofaglar sifatida o'simliklarning turli organlari bilan oziqlanib, jiddiy zarar keltiradi.

Kalit so'zlari

Fitofag, zarar keltiradigan turlar, miqdor zichligi, biotsenotik aloqalar, agrotsenoz, moyli va dukkali ekinlar.

Tunlamsimon kapalaklarning qurtlari tadqiqot hududi janubiy-sharqiy Farg'ona agrotsenozlarida madaniy ekinlar bilan turli darajada trofik aloqalarga ega. Bir qator turlar dominant fitofaglar sifatida o'simliklarning turli organlari bilan oziqlanib, jiddiy zarar keltiradi. Shuningdek, ayrim turlarning qishloq xo'jaligi ekinlari bilan biotsenotik aloqalari quyi darajada yoki tasodifiy shakllangan bo'lib, iqtisodiy zarari deyarli sezilmaydi. Olib borgan tadqiqotlarimiz natijalari va sohaga oid adabiyotlarning tahlillari asosida, tunlamsimon kapalaklarning qurtlarini ozuqa o'simliklariga zarar keltirish darajasiga ko'ra 3 ta pog'onaga ajratdik (1-jadval).

1-jadval

Tunlamsimon turlari	kapalaklar	Ozuqa o'simliklari	Zararlanadigan o'simlik organi	Zarar keltirish darajasi
<i>Lymantria dispar</i> 1758	Linnaeus,	<i>Prunus cerasus</i> L., 1753; <i>Prunus domestica</i> L., 1753;	Barg, yosh novdalar	++

	<i>Malus</i> P. Mill., 1754; <i>Pyrus</i> L., 1753		
<i>Phragmatobia fuliginosa</i> Linnaeus, 1758	<i>Rubus idaeus</i> L., 1753; <i>Rubus fruticosus</i> L., 1753; <i>Vaccinium myrtillus</i> L., 1753	Barg	+
<i>Acantholipes regularis</i> Hübner, 1813	<i>Medicago sativa</i> L., 1753	Barg	+
<i>Dysgonia algira</i> Linnaeus, 1767	<i>Rubus idaeus</i> L., 1753; <i>Rubus fruticosus</i> L., 1753; <i>Vaccinium myrtillus</i> L., 1753	Barg	+
<i>Garella =Erschoviella musculana</i> Erschoff, 1874	Juglandaceae	Barg, generativ organ	++
<i>Diachrysia chrysitis</i> Linnaeus, 1758	<i>Zea mays</i> L., 1753; <i>Medicago</i> L., 1753	Barg	+
<i>Autographa gamma</i> Linnaeus, 1758	Asteraceae, Lamiaceae, Brassicaceae, Rosaceae, Fabaceae	Barg	++
<i>Cornutiplusia circumflexa</i> Linnaeus, 1767	Brassicaceae, Solanaceae	Barg	++
<i>Plusia festucae</i> Linnaeus, 1758	<i>Carex</i> , <i>Iris</i> , <i>Sparganium</i> , <i>Alisma</i> , <i>Betula</i> , <i>Phragmite</i>	Barg	+
<i>Armada panaceorum</i> Ménétrés, 1849	<i>Solanum</i>	Barg	+
<i>Acronicta rumicis</i> Linnaeus, 1758	<i>Rumex</i> , <i>Plantago</i> , <i>Polygonum</i> , <i>Rubus</i> , <i>Salix</i> , <i>Crataegus</i> , <i>Urtica</i>	Barg	++
<i>Cucullia biornata</i> Fischer de Waldheim 1840	<i>Artemisia vulgaris</i>	Barg, generativ organ	+
<i>Schinia scutosa</i> Denis & Schiffermüller, 1775	<i>Pisum</i> L., 1753; <i>Gossypium hirsutum</i> L., 1763; <i>Linum</i> L., 1753; <i>Citrullus lanatus</i> Matsum. & Nakai, 1916;	Barg, generativ organ	++

	<i>Carthamus tinctorius</i> L.; <i>Sesamum</i> L., 1753		
<i>Heliothis nubigera</i> Herrich-Schäffer, 1851	<i>Gossypium hirsutum</i> L., 1763; <i>Phaseolus vulgaris</i> L., 1753; <i>Vigna radiata</i> L. R.Wilczek; <i>Pisum</i> L., 1753; <i>Glycine max</i> Merr.,1917	Barg	++
<i>Heliothis peltigera</i> Denis & Schiffermüller, 1775	<i>Gossypium hirsutum</i> L., 1763; <i>Arachis hypogaea</i> L., 1753; <i>Linum</i> L., 1753; <i>Carthamus tinctorius</i> L.; <i>Ricinus communis</i> L., 1753; <i>Nicotiana tabacum</i> L.; <i>Helianthus</i> L., 1753	Barg, generativ organ	+++
<i>Helicoverpa armigera</i> Hubner, 1808	<i>Gossypium hirsutum</i> L., 1763; <i>Linum</i> L., 1753; <i>Carthamus tinctorius</i> L.; <i>Ricinus communis</i> L., 1753; <i>Nicotiana tabacum</i> L.	Barg, generativ organ	+++
<i>Spodoptera exigua</i> Hübner, 1808	Brassicaceae <i>Hibiscus</i> , <i>Solanum</i> , <i>Nicotiana</i> , <i>Medicago</i> , <i>Cucurbita</i>	Barg, generativ organ	+++
<i>Hydraecia micacea</i> Esper, 1789	<i>Arctium</i> , <i>Iris</i> , <i>Atriplex</i> , <i>Equisetum</i> , <i>Plantago</i> , <i>Phragmites</i> , <i>Rumex</i> , <i>Solanum</i>	Barg, novdalar yosh	++
<i>Amphipoea fucosa</i> Freyer, 1830	<i>Verbascum</i> , <i>Colium</i> , <i>Tragopogon</i> , <i>Rumex</i> , <i>Artemisia</i> , <i>Epilobium</i>	Barg, generativ organ	+
<i>Mesapamea secalis</i> Linnaeus, 1758	<i>Zea mays</i> L., 1753; <i>Medicago</i> L., 1753	Barg	++
<i>Sesamia cretica</i> Lederer, 1857	<i>Zea mays</i> L., 1753; <i>Sorghum halepense</i> Pers., 1805	Barg	+
<i>Cosmia pyralina</i> Denis & Schiffermüller, 1775	<i>Zea mays</i> L., 1753; <i>Sorghum halepense</i> Pers., 1805	Barg	+
<i>Pseudohadena indigna</i> Christoph 1887	<i>Atriplex</i> , <i>Salsola</i> , <i>Chenopodium</i>	Barg	+

<i>Anarta trifolii</i> Hufnagel, 1766	<i>Zea mays</i> L., 1753; <i>Medicago</i> L., 1753	Barg	++
<i>Cardepija sociabilis</i> Graslin, 1850	<i>Zea mays</i> L., 1753	Barg	+
<i>Lacanobia oleracea</i> Linnaeus, 1758	Fabaceae, Brassicaceae,	Barg	++
<i>Mamestra =Barathra brassicae</i> Linnaeus, 1758	Brassicaceae, Fabaceae	Barg	+++
<i>Mythimna l-album</i> Linnaeus, 1767	Gramineae	Barg, yosh novdalar	++
<i>Mythimna unipuncta</i> Haworth, 1809	<i>Zea,</i> <i>Triticum,</i> <i>Hordeum,</i> <i>Glycine, Beta, Medicago,</i> <i>Solanum, Brassica</i>	Barg, yosh novdalar	+++
<i>Leucania loreyi</i> Duponchel, 1827	Gramineae	Barg, generativ organ	++
<i>Leucania zae</i> Duponchel, 1827	Gramineae	Barg, generativ organ	++
<i>Euxoa conspicua</i> Hübner, 1827	<i>Medicago, Gossypium,</i> <i>Helianthus, Nicotiana,</i> <i>Beta, Brassica, Cucumis,</i> <i>Citrullus, Melo,</i> <i>Cucurbita, Hordeum,</i> <i>Triticum, Linum</i>	Barg, yosh novdalar	++
<i>Euxoa tritici</i> Linnaeus, 1761	<i>Helianthus, Beta,</i> <i>Solanum, Populus</i>	Barg, yosh novdalar	+
<i>Euxoa temera</i> Hubner, 1808	<i>Triticum</i> L., 1753, <i>Gossypium hirsutum</i> L., 1763	Barg, generativ organ	+
<i>Dichagyris flammatra</i> Denis & Schiffermüller, 1775	<i>Fragaria, Taraxacum,</i> <i>Triticum, Rubus,</i> <i>Solanum</i>	Ildiz	++
<i>Agrotis exclamationis</i> Linnaeus, 175	<i>Plantago, Rumex,</i> <i>Taraxacum, Artemisia,</i> <i>Spinacia, Fragaria, Beta,</i> <i>Gossypium, Nicotiana,</i> <i>Hibiscus, Zea,</i> <i>Helianthus</i>	Barg	+++
<i>Agrotis ipsilon</i> Hufnagel, 1766	<i>Gossypium, Beta,</i> <i>Plantago, Crataegus,</i> <i>Rumex, Taraxacum,</i> <i>Artemisia, Nicotiana,</i> <i>Solanum, Hibiscus, Zea,</i> <i>Pisum, Sesamum,</i> <i>Medicago, Helianthus</i>	Barg	+++

<i>Agrotis segetum</i> Denis & Schiffermüller, 1775	<i>Beta, Gossypium, Helianthus, Hibiscus, Sesamum, Nicotiana, Solanum, Allium, Daucus, Brassicaceae, Lycopersi, Zea, Convolvulus, Atriplex, Sonchus</i>	Ildiz	+++
<i>Noctua orbona</i> Hufnagel, 1766	<i>Urtica, Rumex, Gramineae, Allium, Rheum, Brassica, Plantago, Solanum,</i>	Ildiz	++
<i>Noctua pronuba</i> Linnaeus, 1758	<i>Gramineae, Allium, Rheum, Brassica, Plantago, Solanum, Spinacia, Taraxacum</i>	Ildiz	++
<i>Xestia c-nigrum</i> Linnaeus, 1758	<i>Amaranthaceae, Fabaceae, Gramineae, Beta, Rubus, Helianthus, Plantago, Rymex</i>	Barg	++

Tadqiqot hududi janubiy-sharqiy Farg'ona agrotsenozlarida kam uchraydigan hamda madaniy o'simliklarga zarari yuqori bo'lmagan (3-ilovada bitta + ishorasi bilan belgilangan) turlar 14 tani (*Phragmatobia fuliginosa, Acantholipes regularis, Dysgonia algira, Diachrysia chrysitis, Plusia festucae, Armada panaceorum, Cucullia biornata, Amphipoea fucosa, Sesamia cretica, Cosmia pyralina, Pseudohadena indigna, Cardepija sociabilis, Euxoa tritici, Euxoa temera*) tashkil etadi (1-diagramma).

1-diagramma

Jumladan, *Phragmatobia fuliginosa* hamda *Dysgonia algira* malina o'simligi bilan trofik aloqaga ega bo'lib, qurtlarining o'simlik barglaridagi zarari deyarli sezilmaydi. Shuningdek, asosan yovvoyi dukkakdoshlarda uchraydigan *Acantholipes regularis*ning qurtlari beda o'simligi bilan ham qisman oziqlanadi. *Diachrysia chrysis* makkajo'huri va bedada, *Cardepija sociabilis*, *Sesamia cretica*, *Cosmia pyralina* makkajo'huri va jo'xorida, *Euxoa tritici*, *Armada panaceorum* sabzovot ekinlarida, *Euxoa temera* bug'doy va g'ozada qisman oziqlanib zarar keltirishi mumkin.

Tadqiqot hududi janubiy-sharqiy Farg'ona agrotsenozlarida ob-havo sharoiti qulay kelgan mavsumlarda jadal ko'payib, qishloq xo'jaligi ekinlariga sezilarli zarar keltiradigan (1-jadvalda ikkita ++ ishorasi bilan belgilangan) turlar soni 19 ta (*Lymantria dispar*, *Garella =Erschoviella musculana*, *Autographa gamma*, *Cornutiplusia circumflexa*, *Acrionicta rumicis*, *Schinia scutosa*, *Heliothis nubigera*, *Hydraecia micacea*, *Mesapamea secalis*, *Anarta trifolii*, *Lacanobia oleracea*, *Mythimna l-album*, *Leucania loreyi*, *Leucania zae*, *Euxoa conspicua*, *Dichagyris flammata*, *Noctua orbona*, *Noctua pronuba*, *Xestia c-nigrum*) dan iborat (1-diagramma). Jumladan, Lymantridae oilasiga mansub bo'lgan *Lymantria dispar* ayrim yillarda tog'oldi mintaqalarga yaqin hududlarda mevali bog'larga ham tarqalib, olma, o'rik daraxtlarining barglari va yosh novdalariga zarar keltiradi. Nolidae oilasiga mansub *Garella* yoki *Erschoviella musculana* (yong'oq qurti)ning zarari ham ob-havo sharoiti qulay kelgan mavsumlarda sezilarli darajada bo'ladi. Tunlam kapalaklardan *Anarta trifolii*,

Mesapamea secalis keng tarqalgan bo'lib, makkajo'gori va bedaning yosh barglariga ayrim yillarda jiddiy zarar keltiradi. *Leucania loreyi*, *Leucania zae* hamda *Mythimna l-album*ning miqdor zichligi yuqori bo'lgan yillarda madaniy g'alladoshlarning barg va generativ organlari jiddiy zararlanishi mumkin. *Euxoa conspicua*, *Autographa gamma*, *Lacanobia oleracea*, *Heliothis nubigera*, *Noctua orbona*, *Noctua pronuba* tunlamlari polifag zararkunanda sifatida bir nechta oilaga mansub madaniy o'simliklar bilan trofik aloqaga ega. Miqdor zichligi yuqori bo'lgan yillarda sabzovot-poliz, dukkakli va ozuqa ekinlariga jiddiy zarar keltirishi mumkin. Shunga o'xshash, *Cornutiplusia circumflexa* Brassicaceae hamda Solanaceae ga mansub madaniy ekinlarda, *Schinia scutosa* g'o'za, moyli va dukkali ekinlarga jiddiy zarar keltiradi.

Tunlamsimon kapalaklarning 8 ta turlari (*Mythimna unipuncta*, *Heliothis peltigera*, *Helicoverpa armigera*, *Spodoptera exigua*, *Mamestra =Barathra brassicae*, *Agrotis exclamationis*, *Agrotis ipsilon*, *Agrotis segetum*) tadqiqot hududi agrotsenoziida dominant fitofaglar sifatida o'simliklarning turli organlari bilan oziqlanib, jiddiy zarar keltiradi (3-ildovada ikkita +++ ishorasi bilan belgilangan) (1-diagramma). Ushbu turlarning barchasi polifag zararkunandalar bo'lib, madaniy ekinlarga zararining yuqoriligi bilan ajralib turadi. Jumladan, *Helicoverpa armigera*, *Heliothis peltigera* asosan g'o'za, shuningdek, dukkakli va sabzovot ekinlarning barg va generativ organlarini shikastlab, hosildorligiga jiddiy ta'sir ko'rsatadi. *Agrotis exclamationis* (undov tunlam), *Agrotis ipsilon* (ipsilon tunlami) va ayniqsa, *Agrotis segetum* (kuzgi tunlam)ning zarari yanada jiddiy bo'lib, deyarli barcha madaniy ekinlar bilan oziqlanib, iqtisodiy zararining yuqoriligi bilan ham ajralib turadi. *Mythimna unipuncta* yoki makkajo'gori tunlamining zarari keyingi yillarda keskin ortib bormoqda.

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